

THE PREVENTION OF PRIMARY CARIES DUE TO THE TIMING OF THE ERUPTION AND MINERALIZATION OF PERMANENT TEETH IN CHILDREN

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Introduction. Numerous clinical observations indicate that caries develops most intensively in the first years after teething, which coincides with the period of immature enamel. Due to the mineralization of enamel, its resistance to caries increases. The terms of eruption and mineralization of permanent teeth in school age children with the physiological development of the child coincide with the terms of complete resorption of the roots of temporary teeth. Eruption and mineralization of permanent teeth is an important aspect of a child's growth and development. Teething is a very complex and not fully understood process. One of the most important stages in the formation of the child's dental system is the period of replacement bite. Monitoring the eruption of permanent teeth and the formation of occlusion is an important point that requires special attention from a pediatric dentist. It is important to emphasize that the study of the features of eruption and mineralization of permanent teeth is of diagnostic and prognostic interest and also justifies the feasibility of dental prevention of school-age children (V. G. Galonsky, A. A. Radkevich, N. V. Tarasova, A. I. Volynkina). To date, in our Republic there are no comprehensive studies on the timing of eruption and reflecting the dynamics of mineralization of the enamel of permanent teeth in children. There is a work By F. L. Mirsalikhova devoted to the study of the degree of mineralization with the timing of eruption of the first permanent molars in children of the city of Tashkent. Based on the above, the study of the timing of eruption and mineralization of permanent teeth in children is very relevant, has great practical and theoretical significance, since the results obtained will be taken into account when organizing dental care for the children's population of our Republic. Most often in our country, mass and collective methods of prevention are used, which, on average, reduce the growth of caries by up to 50%. Carrying out stereotypical prevention, even taking into account regional characteristics, does not allow us to hope for a high end result.

The aim of the research was in vitro investigation of changes in chemical composition and morphological structure of the superficial layer of just erupted 192 © TOSHKENT DAVLAT STOMATOLOGIYA INSTITUTI “YOSH OLIMLAR KUNLARI” 2023 193 permanent teeth enamel under the influence of deep fluoridation. Increased risk of caries in permanent teeth among children and adolescents falls on the period secondary mineralization (5–15 years). The key pathogenetically substantiated direction of caries prevention during this period is the increase degree of mineralization of tooth enamel, which is implemented through the systematic local application of funds prevention, containing various chemical compounds. In the process of mineralization of hard tissues of the tooth, more than 40 chemical elements. The most important of these are calcium and phosphorus, which are the main components of enamel apatites, as well as fluorine, which is considered the most effective element against caries. Some authors indicate the importance of other macro- and microelements, in particular silicon, zinc and magnesium, in the formation of caries-resistant enamel teeth. Therefore, in the last years, attention has been growing to new remineralizing agents, which containing calcium and phosphorus, as well as complex preparations, which additionally contain fluorine, magnesium, silicon and other chemical elements. Studying process control capabilities enamel mineralization permanent teeth through the use of modern means of exogenous prevention of caries is a topical issue dentistry. Years of experience fluorides for the prevention of caries showed them reliability and ability to participate in the remineralization of dental hard tissues. Professional fluoride preparations have advantages over prophylactic agents, due to the higher concentration fluorides contained in them, with the possibility precise application of the agent to the area of demineralization. In the 70s of the last century, Professor A. Knappvost developed a deep fluorination method hard tissues of the teeth. Deep fluorination is based on chemical reactions that occur during the sequential treatment of solid tooth tissues with a solution of magnesium and copper fluoride silicates and a suspension of highly dispersed calcium hydroxide, which leads to the formation fluorosilicate complex. Complex spontaneously breaks down to form microcrystals calcium fluoride, magnesium, copper and polymerized silicic acid. The resulting CaF_2 nanocrystals have a value of 50 Å; therefore, well penetrate into the pores of enamel with a diameter of 100Å. Fluoride crystals are located on the surface and deep in the enamel pores in a thixotropic gel silicic acid, which protects them from washing out. Due to this, a prolonged release of fluorine ions occurs (from six months to 2 years) in a

concentration sufficient for remineralization. In this case, fluorapatite is formed, which provides a complete restoration of the structure enamel in the focus of demineralization with preservation protein matrix. Conclusions. Thus, the results of the study indicate that enamel of just erupted teeth is not mineralized and thus has insufficient resistance to caries. The chemical composition of the superficial layer of tooth enamel changed after using of methods of deep fluoridation of enamel. Achieving of the optimal level of mineralization under the influence of deep fluoridation occurs within 6-months of the experiment. Thus, exogenous agents for the prevention of dental caries (deep fluoridation of enamel) can be recommended for clinical use immediately after the eruption of the teeth within 12 months (1-2 times per year).

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